

ISSN: 3060-4613

MAKTABGACHA
VA MAKTAB
TA'LIMI VAZIRLIGI

№10
2025

- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
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- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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AKTABGACHA VA AKTAB TA'LIMI

Pedagogika, psixologiya fanlariga ixtisoslashgan ilmiy jurnal

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Elektron nashr. 98 sahifa,
3-oktyabr, 2025-yil.

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Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha: OAK Kengashi tavsiyasi (26.08.2024-y., №11-05-4381/01) asosida:

- Ekspert kengashi (29.10.2024-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (31.10.2024-y., №363/5)

Psixologiya fanlari bo‘yicha: Toshkent davlat pedagogika universiteti murojaatiga asosan OAK tavsiyasi (24.04.2025-y., №11-05-2566/01):

- Ekspert kengashi (25.05.2025-y., №10)
- Rayosat qarori (08.05.2025-y., №370/5)

“Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi”
jurnali

26.09.2023-yildan

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti
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va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar
agentligi tomonidan **№C-5669363**
reyestr raqami tartibi bo‘yicha
ro‘yxatdan o‘tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: **№136361**

MUNDARIJA

The Use of Innovative Pedagogical Technologies in the Development of Critical Thinking	16
Gulnar Atakhanova Orinbaevna	
Current Aspects of Designing and Implementing Extracurricular Educational Activities at the Primary General Education Level.....	20
Amankosova Dinara Gabitovna	
Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida tarbiyachi shaxsiyati va kasbiy mahorati shakllanishining nazariy asoslari....	24
Axmadaliyeva Moxlaroy To'xtapolatovna	
Pedagogical Model and Stages of Teaching Subjects Through a Project-Based Approach	28
Bannayev Qosimjon	
Lotin tili va zamonaviy tibbiy terminologiya: tarixi, vazifasi va amaliy ahamiyati	31
Eshmurodova Shirin Oybekovna	
Motor alaliyaning nonutqiy simptomatikasi	34
Isayeva Mushtariy Alisher qizi	
Talabalar etnomadaniy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning pedagogik-psixologik omillari	38
Isomiddinov Asliddin Baxriddin o'g'li	
Texnologiya darslarida o'quvchilarning texnik savodxonligini robototexnika elementlari asosida rivojlantirish.....	41
Jabborova Umida	
Fizika fanini mutaxassislik fanlari integratsiyasi asosida o'qitishda bo'lajak muhandislarning kasbiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari	45
Xayrullayev Asliddin Isatullayevich	
Talaba tomonidan mutaxassislik tilini o'zlashtirishda monologik nutqni o'rgatishning samarali usullari masalasi haqida.....	51
Karimov N. M.	
Zamonaviy pedagog kadrlar tayyorlashda kasbiy motiv va motivatsiyaning o'rni	54
Melikova Elnora Shuxratovna	
Bo'lajak ingliz tili o'qituvchilarini tayyorlashda pragmatik kompetensiyaning roli.....	58
Mustafayeva Nilufar Ulashovna	
O'quvchilarda iqtisodiy tafakkurni rivojlantirishning pedagogik strategiyalari	62
Nishonova Dilafuz	
Computer-Based Formative Assessment: Advantages and Challenges in Teaching English to High School Students	66
Obidjonova Shokhista Bakhtiyorovna	
Metata'lim texnologiyalari asosida bo'lajak maktabgacha ta'lim mutaxassislarini tayyorlash tizimini takomillashtirish.....	70
O'rolboyeva Durдона Sayfiddin qizi	
Sun'iy intellekt asosidagi darslarning an'anaviy darslarga nisbatan samaradorligini qiyosiy tahlil qilish.....	73
Rasulev Bobirjan Atxamovich	
Pedagogik faoliyatda pedagogning kasbiy taraqqiyoti motivatsiyasining psixologik xususiyatlari	78
Rustamova Surayyo Shaxobiddinovna	
Innovatsion kompetentlik tushunchasi va uning ilmiy-pedagogik asoslari.....	84
Soliyev Eliyor Ravshan o'g'li	
Nutqida nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalar eshituv idrokini o'yinlar yordamida rivojlantirishning samarali usullari	88
Xalilova Shahnoza	
Zamonaviy ta'limda kommunikativ kompetensiyaning o'rni va ahamiyati.....	92
Yaqubova Nigoraxon Ibrohimjon qizi	

CURRENT ASPECTS OF DESIGNING AND IMPLEMENTING EXTRACURRICULAR EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES AT THE PRIMARY GENERAL EDUCATION LEVEL

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Master's Degree

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Abstract: The article analyses the problems of organisational and methodological support for class teachers in the context of contemporary socio-cultural conditions. The study highlights conceptual approaches and strategic guidelines that define the modernisation of the educational space, emphasising the role of class hours in developing students' values, communication, and behavioural models. The research outlines the structural, organisational, and methodological components necessary for effective extracurricular educational activities at the primary education level.

Key words: class hour, educational process, development, preparation, structure.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sinf rahbarlarining faoliyatini tashkil etish va metodik qo'llab-quvvatlash masalalari zamonaviy ijtimoiy-madaniy sharoitda tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda ta'lim makonini modernizatsiya qilishni belgilovchi konseptual yondashuvlar va strategik yo'nalishlar asosida sinf soatining o'quvchilarda qadriyatlar, kommunikativ ko'nikmalar hamda xulqiy modellarning shakllanishidagi o'rni yoritilgan. Shuningdek, boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichida sinfdan tashqari ta'limiy faoliyatni samarali tashkil etish uchun zarur bo'lgan tarkibiy, tashkiliy va metodik omillar ko'rsatib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: sinf soati, ta'lim jarayoni, rivojlantirish, tayyorlash, tuzilma.

Аннотация: В статье анализируются проблемы организационно-методической поддержки классных руководителей в условиях современных социально-культурных реалий. В исследовании рассматриваются концептуальные подходы и стратегические ориентиры модернизации образовательного пространства, подчёркивается роль классного часа в формировании у учащихся ценностей, коммуникативных навыков и моделей поведения. Определены структурные, организационные и методические компоненты, необходимые для эффективной реализации внеурочной образовательной деятельности на уровне начального образования.

Ключевые слова: классный час, образовательный процесс, развитие, подготовка, структура.

INTRODUCTION

Class hour is recognised as one of the key forms of organising the educational process, performing educational, orientational, guiding, and formative functions. According to N.E. Shchurkova's conceptualisation, it represents a purposefully organised and value-oriented activity aimed at cultivating in students a stable system of attitudes towards reality. In this regard, class hour not only serves as a pedagogical tool for transmitting knowledge but also functions as an effective mechanism for shaping social behaviour, developing communication skills, and strengthening moral values. Therefore, it plays a crucial role in the overall development of primary school pupils, ensuring the integration of educational content with socio-cultural requirements and strategic guidelines for the modernisation of the educational space.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The organisation of extracurricular educational activities in primary schools has been widely discussed by both classical and contemporary scholars. Shchurkova in 1999 conceptualised the class hour as a value-oriented pedagogical activity with a clear organisational structure, linking objectives, content, and assessment.

Mukhina in 1999 highlighted the psychological features of primary school children, emphasising that at this age learning activities and communication experiences are central to cognitive and social development. Dewey in 1938 argued that learning should be grounded in experience, which directly supports the idea that extracurricular programmes encourage reflection and active participation. Similarly, Bronfenbrenner in 1979, through his ecological systems theory, explained that a child's development is shaped by interactions across family, school, and community contexts, which underscores the need for extracurricular activities to be designed in harmony with these systems.

Empirical studies also demonstrate the positive outcomes of extracurricular engagement. Marsh and Kleitman in 2002 found a strong relationship between participation in school clubs and both academic achievement and self-esteem. Eccles and Barber in 1999 showed that involvement in structured activities, such as sports or arts, fosters motivation and strengthens social identity. More recent meta-analyses by Durlak, Weissberg, and Pachan in 2010 confirmed that well-designed programmes significantly improve social-emotional skills, behaviour, and academic performance. These findings collectively affirm that extracurricular activities, when systematically organised and age-appropriate, are powerful tools for promoting holistic development in primary education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

From a structural standpoint, class time constitutes a multifunctional and flexible system that permits variation in methods, forms, and means in accordance with pedagogical objectives. This variation is intended to develop the optimal scenario for its implementation.

In the context of the development of the student personality, it is customary to classify class hours into the following types:

- a) The objective of this programme is to facilitate personality development.
- b) The development of the emotional sphere is the primary focus.
- c) The objective of this approach is to facilitate the establishment of behavioural models.

The development of a class hour, for example, dedicated to the promotion of a healthy lifestyle among younger schoolchildren, involves the design of activities focused on the acquisition of knowledge and skills in the field of healthy lifestyles, the development of teamwork and interpersonal skills, as well as the formation of students' subjective positions.

A fundamental element in the organisation of the event pertains to the consideration of the age and psychological characteristics of the audience. Consequently, at the primary school age, educational activities emerge as the predominant factor. As V.S. Mukhina observes: *"In addition to acquiring specific cognitive skills and competencies related to writing, reading, drawing, work, and so forth, guided by a teacher, children commence the mastery of the content of the fundamental forms of human consciousness and are instructed in the manner of acting in accordance with established traditions and emerging social expectations. In new relationships with adults and peers, the child continues to develop reflection on themselves and others."*

Consequently, the design of a class hour for the specified age group should be focused on cognitive enrichment and the formation of new models of interpersonal interaction.

As with any educational event, a class hour is characterised by a clearly defined organisational structure:

1. The determination of the topic, objectives, and participants is a fundamental step in the process. The most relevant and significant topic for primary school pupils is that of healthy lifestyles. It is evident that the objectives under discussion align with the overarching goals of the class hour, as previously delineated. The target demographic is primary school pupils.
2. The selection of a location. The most preferable and pedagogically justified option is to hold the event in the classroom assigned to the class. This approach is theorised to assist in minimising distractions and reducing the cognitive load associated with adapting to a novel environment.
3. The development of the script. This stage is characterised by its complexity and the significant investment of time it demands, owing to the presence of an internal structure. Initially, the establishment of emotional contact with the audience, in conjunction with the introduction procedure, assumes considerable significance. It is important to acknowledge that the communication skills of younger schoolchildren are not yet fully developed. Initially, they replicate the communication style they have learned in their family environment. The development of an individual's communication style is a gradual process that occurs as they assimilate into a new social group. The optimal format for initial familiarisation is an interactive game.

One such example is a game known as “Hello”. The game’s mechanism is as follows: the host makes a statement or poses a question, and the students respond with “Hello!” if they agree with the statement. For example:

A cordial salutation is extended to those who have engaged in physical activity during the designated morning hours.

Greetings!

Secondly, upon establishing initial contact, the moderator (in this case, the class teacher) is required to deliver an introductory speech. The purpose of this speech is twofold: firstly, to explain the purpose of the upcoming activity to the participants, and secondly, to help strengthen positive group dynamics.

Consequently, the design of class hours for primary school pupils should be aimed at cognitive enrichment and the development of new models of interpersonal interaction.

As with any educational activity, class hours are subject to a specific organisational structure:

1. The formulation of topics and objectives, in addition to the determination of participants, is a fundamental aspect of the process. The most relevant and socially significant topic for primary school pupils is that of healthy lifestyles. The objectives of the event correspond to the general educational objectives of the class hour outlined above. The participants are pupils in the initial stage of general education.
2. The selection of a suitable venue is a critical component of the planning process. It appears that the most suitable location for the event would be the classroom designated for the class. This approach serves to minimise external distractions and reduce the cognitive load associated with adapting to a novel environment.
3. The development of a scenario is underway. This stage is characterised by its complexity and the significant utilisation of resources, owing to the presence of an internal structure. Firstly, it is imperative to establish productive emotional contact with the audience. It is important to acknowledge that the communication skills of younger schoolchildren are still developing and initially reproduce the models learned in the family environment. The development of an individual’s communication style is a gradual process that occurs as the individual integrates into the group. The most efficacious format for initial familiarisation appears to be the utilisation of interactive game techniques.

One method that has been employed is the utilisation of a game known as “Hello”, in which the host makes a statement and the students respond with “Hello!” if they agree with it. For example:

A cordial salutation is extended to those who have engaged in physical activity during the designated morning hours.

Greetings!

Secondly, upon establishing initial contact, the moderator (class teacher) is required to deliver an introductory speech, in which they are expected to reveal the objectives and content of the upcoming activity, as well as establish the rules of conduct during the event.

4. The content and organisational block are the subjects of this text. The subsequent stage in the programme is the development of the content and the selection of appropriate formats for the event.

A plethora of methodologies can be employed to organise a class hour, including but not limited to: debates, discussions, round tables, conferences, lectures, quizzes, relay races, and intellectual games. The choice is determined by the goals set.

For younger schoolchildren, the most effective format appears to be a quiz accompanied by explanatory commentary. This enables the initiation of cognitive activity through a competitive element, whilst the informational additions provide cognitive enrichment.

The organisation of a quiz is typically a task that demands collaboration among team members. The formation of teams by means of a random draw is to be recommended. For instance, upon entering the auditorium, each student selects a token from a bag with a number that determines their place at the corresponding table.

It is imperative that text materials and task formulations be adapted to the age-specific characteristics of perception. The utilisation of crossword puzzles has been demonstrated to engender additional cognitive interest. This pedagogical technique enables students to focus on the game process, with each participant independently filling in the corresponding cells with the correct answer. In order to facilitate the visualisation of the results, it is recommended that a board with a clear display of points or other activity-tracking symbols be utilised.

It is recommended that informative comments be provided following each answer, with the aim of elucidating the significant aspects of the phenomenon under discussion. Alternatively, the initiation of a brief discussion may be beneficial, by way of requesting additional information from the teams on the topic.

5. The subsequent stage is one of reflection and evaluation. When synthesising the results, it is imperative to consider both quantitative indicators, such as points scored, and qualitative aspects of the teams' activity. In order to enhance group cohesion, it is recommended that a festival principle be employed, incorporating nominations and the conferring of symbolic prizes or certificates to all participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A mandatory component of the final part of the programme is a reflective discussion and the concluding remarks delivered by the class teacher. Such reflection allows participants to evaluate not only the outcomes of the activity but also the process of its organisation and implementation. It is recommended that specialists, such as school psychologists and social pedagogues, observe the behaviour of students for the subsequent analysis of the event's effectiveness. Their professional assessment can help to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the class hour, determine its impact on students' cognitive and emotional development, and provide valuable recommendations for improvement in future educational activities.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

It is evident that the organisation of class hours in primary schools necessitates a systematic approach to the design of structural components, encompassing the target, content, organisational and activity, as well as assessment and analysis aspects. This approach is further compounded by the necessity to take into account the age and individual characteristics of students. Therefore, the effectiveness of class hours depends on a comprehensive methodology that unites pedagogical objectives with the socio-psychological needs of learners. It is also advisable that teachers, alongside school psychologists and social pedagogues, continuously improve the content and methods of such activities, ensuring their relevance to contemporary educational requirements and fostering the holistic development of pupils.

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 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

Mas'ul muharrir: Ramzidin Ashurov

Ingliz tili muharriri: Murod Xoliyorov

Musahhih: Alibek Zokirov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Iskandar Islomov

2025. №10

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"Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi" jurnali 26.09.2023-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №C-5669363 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: № 136361.

Manzirimiz: Toshkent shahar, Yunusobod tumani
19-mavze, 17-uy.